

THE BASIC MEASURES TO ENSURE THE SECURITY OF THE DIGITAL ARCHIVAL DOCUMENTS IN THE CONDITIONS OF WAR WITH RUSSIA

Volodymyr Mikhalko

*candidate of technical sciences,
senior researcher, associate professor,
senior researcher of the department
of technological support of archival affairs,
The Ukrainian research institute of archival affairs and records keeping,
Ukraine
v.mikhalko.undiasd@arch.gov.ua
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-5586-3570>*

Abstract – The purpose of the article is to develop the package of basic measures to ensure the security of digital archival documents based on the results of the analysis of the activities of archival institutions of Ukraine in the conditions of war with Russia. Ensuring the security of digital archival documents during the armed aggression of Russia is an integral part of preserving the historical and cultural heritage of the Ukrainian people. The process of ensuring the security of digital archival documents in the conditions of the active hostilities (and primarily we are talking about digital archival documents of the National Archival Holdings (hereinafter – NAH)) requires archival institutions to develop and implement the package of preventive and active measures in order to minimize the consequences of the active hostilities, such as theft, destruction, or damage to the digital archival documents. The research method comprises the application of special-scientific (historical-source analysis) and general-scientific (analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization) methods. The specificity of the topic under study involves the use of empirical research methods that reveal the ways of systematic development of the state archives in the conduct of active hostilities on the territory of Ukraine. Scientific novelty. The article proposes a package of basic measures to ensure the security of digital archival documents in conditions of active hostilities. Analysis of the situation with damage and destruction of archival documents, including digital archival documents, in Ukraine must become an impetus for reviewing the regulation of financial, personnel, information, and material support for the

development of archival institutions in Ukraine and in the world, because it is archival institutions that preserve the creative heritage of national science and culture.

Submission Type – Short Paper.

Keywords – preservation of digital archival documents, digitalization, evacuation, active hostilities.

Conference Topics – Haerenga – Journey.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ukraine, being in the unprecedented circumstances of a full-scale Russian invasion of its territory, is forced to seek effective ways to protect the archival documents, including digital archival documents. The process of ensuring the security of digital archival documents in conditions of active hostilities requires the archival institutions to develop and implement a package of preventive and active measures in order to minimize the consequences of active hostilities, such as theft, destruction, or damage of the digital archival documents.

II. MAIN TEXT OF ARTICLE

Since the beginning of the full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine, because of active hostilities, the digital archival documents of the state archives of Kharkiv, Mykolaiv, and Kyiv regions [1] and the state archival institutions of Dnipro, Mykolaiv, Sumy,

Kharkiv, and Kherson regions [2] have been damaged and destroyed.

Considering the scale of damage and destruction of digital archival documents, as well as in order to minimize the consequences of the active hostilities, such as theft, damage, or destruction of the digital archival documents, it is advisable for archival institutions to carry out the following measures:

- to plan the measures to organize and conduct the evacuation of digital archival documents, in particular, develop an "Evacuation Plan for archival documents (digital archival documents)." In the event of a decision to evacuate an archival institution, the evacuation, storage, and destruction of the National Archival Holdings documents are carried out under the "Procedure for ensuring the evacuation, storage, and the "Methodology for planning evacuation measures" [3]. According to [3], the process of evacuating digital archival documents includes packing, moving, and transporting to a designated location of the media on which digital archival documents are stored. Since digital archival documents can be stored on physically separate media (of various types), servers, cloud storage, etc., this aspect must be taken into account when planning evacuation measures, in particular, to provide for appropriate packaging materials, equipment, and vehicles. In order to protect digital archival documents and their documentary information, joint and simultaneous transportation or movement of media on which digital archival documents are stored from the main and insurance funds is not recommended, since in the event of an additional emergency (fire, traffic accident, consequences of active hostilities, etc.), both the originals and backup copies of the documents may be damaged or destroyed, which will lead to their complete loss and the impossibility of recovery;

- to organize and conduct an expert appraisal of the value of the digital archival documents to determine the value and storage terms of documents depending on their historical, scientific, cultural, and aesthetic significance for forming the NAH. In particular, it is proposed to divide the digital archival documents into categories depending on the level of their value. Thus, depending on the value of the digital archival documents, the order of their evacuation and the degree of ensuring their security are determined;

- to replenish security and remote fonds (archive groups) of the digital archival documents with security copies of the digital archival documents. According to the recommendations of specialized international organizations, in particular "The Digital Preservation Coalition," and several national archives in Europe [4], in order to ensure the security of information of digital archival documents, it is advisable to create three copies of the original digital document. One copy is recommended to be stored in cloud storage, and the other two copies - in the fonds (archive groups) on different types of digital media. This approach coincides with the basic cybersecurity rule for data backup - the "3-2-1" rule (have at least three copies of data; store copies on at least two media; keep at least one backup copy remotely) [5]. Based on the results of the analysis of the experience of archival institutions of Ukraine in combat conditions, as well as in order to effectively ensure the safety of digital archival documents, it is necessary for archives to create the following three backup copies:

- backup copy 1 of the original of digital archival document is stored physically away from the original. In this case, it is allowed that backup copy 1 is stored in the same territory as the original document, but necessarily in a different room. Backup copies 1 should be stored on information carriers that differ in type from the information carriers of the original of digital archival document (this can be offline storage on LTO magnetic tapes, HDD or SSD external removable disks or internal storage devices of server equipment);

- backup copy 2 of the original of digital archival document is stored remotely. It is necessary that the premises where backup copies 2 will be stored are physically remote from the place where the original and their backup copy 1 are stored. It is recommended to organize the storage of backup copies 2 in an archive storage in another building or a geographically remote settlement on media that differ in type from the media of the original document. Thus, if the original documents are stored on internal drives of server equipment, backup copies 1 - on LTO tapes, external removable SSD disks, then backup copies 2 should be stored on external removable HDD disks;

- backup copy 3 of the original of digital archival document is stored remotely in a virtual (online) cloud storage. When storing backup copies in cloud

storage, it is recommended to configure automatic backup of information to the cloud.;

– one of the effective and efficient ways to ensure the safety of the digital archival documents is to use the capabilities of cloud storage to place their digital (electronic) copies in them. The practical use of cloud storage capabilities by the state archives of Ukraine has become a necessary element of ensuring reliable storage of the digital archival documents, which has prevented their theft, destruction, or damage because of objective factors of the present day. In fact, archival institutions began to use cloud services to store digital (electronic) copies of the archival documents in the first months of Russia's armed aggression against Ukraine. Already, in February 2022, Ukrainian archivists received proposals from foreign colleagues to store digital data in cloud storage outside Ukraine for their security. On March 15, 2022, the Parliament of Ukraine amended Article 5 of the Law of Ukraine “On information protection in information and communication systems” [6], according to which information owners could conclude agreements with foreign companies and organizations that are cloud service providers during the period of the martial law legal regime in Ukraine and six months after its termination or cancellation. On March 25, 2022. An agreement was concluded between the State Archival Service of Ukraine and the National Archives of the United Kingdom (Great Britain) “On the backup storage of digital copies of documents of the state archives of Ukraine in the cloud storage of foreign partners” [7], under the terms of which the National Archives of the United Kingdom provided cloud storage of sufficient size based on the Amazon Web Services (AWS) cloud services platform free. This enabled state archival institutions to organize storing copies of archival documents of the state archives in case of loss or damage to their originals because of hostilities on the territory of Ukraine;

– to build or equip special, including underground storage facilities in archival institutions for reliable storage of all types of archival documents;

– to continue monitoring the conditions of preservation of cultural values and the documents of the NAH of the state archival institutions in wartime conditions [2];

– to continue monitoring the safety of cultural and material values – documents of the NAH of Ukraine that were stolen, lost, or destroyed because of a full-scale invasion of the Russian Federation [2];

– strengthen the material and technical base of state archival institutions, including by involving international humanitarian aid and financial resources of the donor community to meet their needs in martial law;

– in order to increase the efficiency of preserving the digital archival documents, strengthen cooperation with archival institutions of Ukraine's partner countries (exchange of experience, internships of archival institution employees, possible placement of the remote fonds, and integration into the European archival community).

III. CONCLUSION

Analysis of the situation with damage and destruction of the digital archival documents in Ukraine must become an impetus for reviewing the state regulation of financial, personnel, information, and material support for the development of archival institutions in Ukraine and in the world, because it is archival institutions that preserve the creative heritage of national science and culture of the countries. As a result of an applied study of the problems of ensuring the safety of digital archival documents in conditions of active hostilities on the territory of Ukraine, a scheme for the permanent storage of such documents was developed, which meets the modern needs of archives. An analysis of the experience of measures taken to ensure the security of the digital archival documents by the archival institutions of Ukraine during Russia's armed aggression against Ukraine shows that the effective organization and implementation of these measures requires careful planning; financial assistance from international donors, and a high professional and organizational level of employees of archival institutions.

REFERENCES

- [1] Kulyk I. Ukrainian Archives: Destruction and Repetition – Rashists and Communists. URL: <https://www.istpravda.com.ua/articles/2023/06/9/162784/> (accessed April 7, 2025).
- [2] On the work of the State Archival Service of Ukraine, archival institutions and special institutions of the documentation insurance fond in 2023 and priorities

for 2024. Kyiv: State Archival Service of Ukraine. 2024. 75 p.

- [3] L. Didukh, V. Mikhalko and Y. Chornimorets Methodological recommendations "The ensuring the preservation of digital audiovisual documents of the National Archival Holdings" / State Archival Service of Ukraine, Ukrainian scientific research institute of archival affairs and reports keeping, Ukraine: Kyiv, 2024. 185 p.
- [4] Digital Preservation Assessment. Handbook / Northeast Document Conservation Center. Andover, Massachusetts. 2019. URL: <https://www.nedcc.org/assets/media/documents/nedcc-DPA-hndbk-6.24-web.pdf> (accessed April 3, 2025).
- [5] ISO 14641:2018 «Electronic document management – Design and operation of an information system for the preservation of electronic documents – Specifications». 40 p. URL: <https://www.iso.org/ru/standard/74338.html> (accessed April 7, 2025).
- [6] On the Protection of Information in Information and Communication Systems: Law of Ukraine dated 05.07.1994 No. 80/94-VR: URL: <https://ips.ligazakon.net/document/Z008000?an=4801> (accessed April 5, 2025).
- [7] The First Agreement on backup storage of digital copies of documents of the National Archival Holdings of Ukraine in cloud storages of foreign partners. URL: <http://surl.li/qqgufc> (accessed April 5, 2025).

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Volodymyr Mikhalko, candidate of technical sciences, associate professor.

Senior researcher of the department of technological support of archival affairs, the Ukrainian Research Institute of Archival Affairs and Record Keeping.

I have more than 15 years of experience in educational and scientific organizations. Author and co-author of 95 scientific works (articles, conference papers, textbooks and manuals).

